

Evaluating the accuracy of the Biostrap wrist-worn Photoplethysmography sensor in measuring resting heart rate versus a single-lead ECG device

Kerry Martin¹, Kevin Longoria¹, Reinier van Mourik¹, Willem Gielen¹

¹ Biostrap, Duarte, CA, United States

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Corresponding Author:

Kerry Martin, Phd
Biostrap USA LLC
1811 Business
Center Drive
Duarte CA 91010
United States

Phone: (323)999-4757
Email: kerry@biostrap.com

Abstract

Introduction: Photoplethysmography (PPG) is a popular method for determining heart rate (HR) but the accuracy of most wrist-worn heart rate monitoring using PPG monitors is still uncertain. This study compares the Biostrap EVO sensor's PPG-derived resting heart rate (RHR) with a medically certified ECG device as a gold standard.

Methods: This study included 12 healthy adults with a mean (SD) age of 44 (14.4) years, BMI of 24.1 (3.9), and 9 females (75 percent). Participant ECG recordings were collected with the MyDiagnostick for 1 minute while their heart rate was recorded by a Biostrap EVO wrist-worn device (Biostrap USA LLC, Duarte, USA). A Bland-Altman plot was constructed to show heart rate agreement.

Discussion: The Biostrap EVO wrist-worn sensor's PPG-derived resting heart rate was compared with a single-lead ECG. The PPG signal and ECG recording were significantly comparable in terms of resting heart rate. The readings were unaffected by BMI, age, or gender. These findings open the door for long-term remote patient monitoring using a PPG-enabled wearable device.

Conclusion: Despite the study's limitations, we can say that the Biostrap EVO wrist-worn wearable with PPG technology can accurately determine RHR.

Introduction

Resting heart rate (RHR) is an important measurement for clinicians while observing acute and chronic health patterns. Being able to quickly and easily identify RHR is valuable in both clinical and commercial settings, which is why many technologies exist, each with different advantages and disadvantages. The current gold-standard method for heart rate detection is the electrocardiogram (ECG), which measures electrical activity of the heart. While ECG is widely used for its accuracy, equipment tends to be larger and more expensive, and requires a robust signal filtration system; this often makes ECG technology less portable and attainable.

Photoplethysmography (PPG) is a popular method for determining heart rate (HR) [1]. Since 1977, when Seppo Säynäjäkangas, a professor at Finland's University of Oulu, developed the first battery-powered fingertip heart rate monitor as a training tool for the Finnish National Cross Country Ski team, this technology has become smaller and more reliable, with inclusion into many 'form factors' (body interfaces), such as earlobe clips, toe clips, finger rings, and watch-style wristbands. Due to the advent of smartwatches as consumer wearables, the wrist has been the focus of many PPG devices.

While the accuracy of fingertip heart rate monitoring has been well-validated for clinical use and monitoring [2], the accuracy of most wrist-worn heart rate monitors using PPG monitors is still uncertain [3,4]. The aim of this study is to compare the accuracy of the Biostrap EVO wrist-worn sensor's PPG-derived resting heart rate with an ECG as a gold standard.

Methods

Twelve healthy adults were recruited for this study. The mean (standard deviation) age was 43.8 (± 14.4) years; the mean (standard deviation) body mass index (calculated as weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared) was 24.1 (± 3.9); and 9 participants were female (75%) (table 1). Cardiovascular disease, pacemakers, and treatment with heart rhythm medications were all exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria were age of at least 18 years old and ability to offer written informed permission in Danish.

Participants were instructed to hold the MyDiagnostick (MyDiagnostick Medical B.V., Maastricht, the Netherlands) for 1 minute (figure 1) while their heart rate was simultaneously recorded with a Biostrap EVO wrist-worn device (Biostrap USA LLC, Duarte, USA) (figure 2) worn above the ulnar styloid.

Statistical analysis

Processed heart rates from both MyDiagnostick and Biostrap EVO (1 min. averages) were recorded for each individual. Agreement between the heart rates was assessed by the concordance correlation coefficient and visualized by a Bland-Altman plot (figure 3).

Analyses were performed using R version 4.0.3 (DescTools and ggplot2 packages required) (table 2).

Figure 1. The MyDiagnostick is a medical device which has to be held with both hands for one minute to record a high-quality single-lead ECG.

Figure 2. The Biostrap EVO device is a wrist-worn wearable configurable red/IR photoplethysmography (PPG) and motion detecting device which collects raw pulse wave signals to estimate vital signs, sleep parameters, and physical activity.

Results

Subject	Biostrap EVO (bpm)	MyDiagnostick (bpm)	Age (yrs)	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	BMI (kg/m ²)
1	93	91	48	174	90	29.7
2	79	79	37	164	58	21.6
3	73	72	29	165	82	30.1
4	63	65	61	174	59	19.5
5	69	69	60	167	64	22.9
6	64	65	35	164	56	20.8
7	66	67	39	189	85	23.8
8	55	54	36	182	75	22.6
9	75	73	66	179	65	20.3
10	65	65	58	168	60	21.3
11	80	81	34	167	80	28.7
12	65	66	22	165	75	27.5

Table 1. Heart rates (bpm) obtained by each device and the characteristics for each of the twelve subjects.

Figure 3. A Bland-Altman plot representing the difference between heart rates as observed by the MyDiagnostick and Biostrap EVO devices. The blue line represents the mean difference between measures of heart rate; red lines represent the 95% confidence interval of the mean differences.

Statistic	Value	(95% CI)
Concordance Correlation Coefficient	0.989	(0.963, 0.997)
Mean difference	-0.19	(-0.90, 0.52)
Standard Deviation of Difference	1.21	(0.85, 2.14)

Table 2. Agreement statistics

Discussion

In this study, we compared the PPG-derived resting heart rate of the Biostrap EVO wrist-worn sensor with a single-lead ECG. Resting HR derived from the PPG signal and ECG recordings showed a precise and significant correlation. Furthermore, body mass index, age, and gender had no effect on monitor accuracy. These results pave the way for the PPG-enabled wearable device to be used not only for diagnostics, but also for long-term remote patient monitoring.

A limitation in this study is that the sample size is small and may not represent all individuals who may use the device, though the range of age was relatively wide. Additionally, the average BMI of 24.1 kg/m² is lower than most country averages, suggesting a healthier cohort of participants. While there is minimal data to suggest that red and infrared light PPG is affected by anthropometry, demographics, or comorbidities, further investigations using larger sample sizes should be performed.

It is worth noting that the MyDiagnostick has shown validation among various heart rate measures, but does have its limitations. In a prior validation study, MyDiagnostic noted that results from the device are accurate when compared to a 12-lead ecg, but may be subject to some external factors such as tremors of the hands, very dry skin, or vertical heart alignment [5]. Red and infrared light PPG, as used in the Biostrap EVO, is subject to motion artifacts which can make HR detection difficult. However, the Biostrap EVO confidence-tests the raw PPG data and only uses waveforms which do not contain motion artifacts.

These data presented support that the Biostrap EVO red and infrared light wrist-worn PPG sensor accurately captures resting heart rate when compared with an ECG device. No other outcome variables from the Biostrap EVO device were examined as outcome measures. As such, further studies are required to validate other features of the PPG waveform, including respiratory rate, SpO₂, atrial fibrillation, and arterial stiffness.

Conclusion

The Biostrap EVO wrist-worn wearable with PPG technology can determine RHR with high accuracy when compared to ECG. Further studies should determine accuracy under atypical conditions, including stress and health levels, postures, environmental conditions, and activities.

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